

UNIQUE CHARACTERISTICS OF LEXEMES RELATED TO MARRIAGE IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This article discusses the unique characteristics of lexemes related to marriage of the peoples of the world, the similarities and differences between them.

Keywords: marriage, bride, groom, cake cutting, throwing flowers, white dress, friends, relatives, money, gift, bouquet, religious speech

It is known that there are various customs related to marriage in the countries of the world, which are strikingly similar and different from each other. For example, we can observe that the expression of cutting the wedding cake together (das gemeinsame Anschneiden der Hochzeitstorte) is coming to different countries, including us. In Buda, the bride and groom hold a knife decorated with ribbons together and cut four, give them to each other, and then distribute the cut four to others.

The fact that the bride wears a white wedding dress (das weiße Brautkleid) on the day of the wedding ceremony also has a symbolic meaning.

It is known from the research that wearing white clothes was first started by the nobles of the Renaissance period in the Western countries belonging to the Christian religion, but this custom did not become widespread until the end of the 19th century. [1:36]

White color was a symbol of purity, elegance and light. Usually, the bride goes shopping with her mother and friends. It was understood that the bride's chosen white dress was only allowed to be seen by the groom at the wedding, otherwise it would bring bad luck. According to superstition, this situation is believed to mean that the demons may look at her badly in the presence of her future husband. [2:04.03.23]

In addition, white color also means virginity. The lexeme of a white wedding dress (er weiße Brautschleier) is also important in a certain sense. Often on the day of the wedding, the bride and groom's parents hold the bride and groom's head in a wide open position. Under a white sheet, the bride and groom dance together. After a while, the groom's relatives dance with the bride, and the bride's relatives or friends dance with the groom. Before dancing, they have to throw money on a white sheet. In this way, the money collected from those who danced is presented to the newlyweds as the next wedding gift. [3:46] Even today, this tradition is carried out in different forms.

Items such as something old, something new, something blue and something borrowed (Etwas Altes, etwas Neues, etwas Blaues und etwas Geborgtes) have a special place in the wedding ceremony. This custom came from England, and today it has become a custom in other western countries.

An antique is usually a piece of jewelry that represents a family heirloom or something your mother wore to a wedding. This custom not only means connection with the origin and family, but also the strength of the relationship.

The new thing represents happiness and the bride's hopes for a bright future. It also represents a new phase of life. It usually consists of a wedding dress, flowers or rings. [1:42]

Many brides and grooms borrow something from their friends because it symbolizes support no matter what the situation or life's trials. Usually this is a bag or jewelry.

The blue thing usually means the blue flower in the hair. The color blue has long represented loyalty, purity, honesty, love and humility. So this color is very common in weddings. [1:64]

There is a German saying: Andere Länder, andere Sitten (Different countries, different customs). In almost all countries of the world, the wedding ceremony consists of jokes, various games, dances and songs. In addition to the above-mentioned traditions, we can observe that many countries of the world have different customs and customs.

For example, according to wedding customs in the United States, two to six weeks before the wedding, the bride and her friends have a "bridal shower" together. They receive baby dishes and household items as gifts. They usually drink alcohol. Many couples even practice eating dinner together the day before the wedding. Only the closest friends and relatives are invited to the wedding ceremony and formal dinner.

Polish weddings are characterized by a radical difference from the customs of other countries. In order for the bride and groom to have a wedding ceremony in Poland, they have to go through some obstacles. The groom will have to negotiate with the bride's neighbors, friends and colleagues in various ways, and get permission to drive a car with his future wife. Before the bride and groom leave the church, they receive various congratulations and wishes for their life together from their parents and close family members. The music group plays sad songs and music because they have lost their childhood to a new life. It is customary for some of the gathered people to shed tears over this situation. It is customary for the guests to throw coins to the bride and groom during the viewing. The bride and groom should take the coins that are thrown, meaning prosperity. [3:78]

Lexemes such as bakal, wine, kiss, and sheet dance play an important role in the marriage ceremony. At the wedding reception, the bride and groom drink from linked bowls, symbolizing the bond between the two. After drinking the first sparkling wine, the bride and groom immediately throw the bowl over their shoulders. During the ceremony, the bride and groom are encouraged to kiss each other in front of the entire wedding party. It is accompanied by the repeated shouts of "Gorzko" from the guests urging them to kiss.

At midnight in Poland there is a dance under the sheets, like in German folk. The bride's friends form a circle around the bride and try to prevent the groom from coming to the bed. After the groom enters the veil, it is customary for the bride to turn her back and throw a bouquet of flowers to her friends with her eyes closed. They believe that a girl who catches this will have to get married.

The most interesting thing is that in Poland, the grooms should also throw the tie that the bride took off to the groomsmen. There is a picture that says that if an unmarried young man from among the bridegrooms catches the toss, he will be the next bridegroom. [1:56]

"Sofreh Aghd" means a white wedding dress made of silk and decorated with lace. In the East, in Arab countries, a carpet is laid on the floor, and the bride and groom sit on it.

During the ceremony, the imam delivers a religious lecture. It is customary for a Muslim wedding to be read by an imam or a mullah. Before the marriage, the consent of the bride and groom is asked. After the groom agrees to the wedding, the bride is asked. According to custom, the bride answers the question on the third repetition. According to custom, the bride and groom give each other rings and give each other honey from a jar during this ceremon. [2:04.03.23]

In conclusion, it can be said that knowing the customs of different peoples, including identifying the similarities and differences between the marriage ceremony, is one of the urgent problems of comparative linguistics.

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